

Preliminary results of the monitoring of protected red wood ants in Rila Mountain, Bulgaria

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Abstract: This study aimed to assess the present distribution of red wood ant species and changes in their nest density over a period of eight years in the area of Rila Mt, Bulgaria. One of the sampling areas was the Parangalitsa Biosphere Reserve, the nation's second oldest protected area. The other two sites are Rila Monastery region and Samokov region. Field monitoring via transect sampling was conducted in 2014 and 2022. We marked 35 nests along 29 transects in 2014 and 76 nests along 27 transects in 2022 of the red wood ants *Formica rufa* Linnaeus, 1761, *F. lugubris* Zetterstedt, 1838, *F. pratensis* Retzius, 1783, and *F. exsecta* Nylander, 1846, the latter of which is not a member of the *rufa* group. The most abundant species was *F. rufa*, followed by *F. lugubris*, *F. pratensis*, and *F. exsecta*. The nest density of *F. rufa* and *F. pratensis* decreased in some of the revisited transects after 8 years, which can be explained by increased shading of their habitats. Monitoring is recommended at least every 5 years to detect trends in red wood ant populations and evaluate the effects of protection measures.

Keywords: *Formica rufa* group, IUCN red list species, nest density, shading effect

Introduction

Role of red wood ants

The *Formica rufa* species group, known as red wood ants (RWA), plays a crucial role in nutrient cycling in predator-prey systems (Gösswald, 1990). They act as ecological engineers in forested ecosystems, contributing to habitat and soil modification, seed dispersion and plant/tree growth (Stockan & Robinson, 2016). Their mounds are home to more than 100 invertebrate myrmecophilous species (Robinson & Stockan, 2020). Members of the *rufa* group are territorial species and the viability of a single colony requires a few hectares of habitat and associated food resources (Sorvari, 2016). They have wide multi-trophic interactions as they are predators of many insects, mutualists with aphids and are food for many

arthropods, birds and vertebrates (Stockan & Robinson, 2016). Red wood ants are scavengers and generalist predators that prey on many insect groups, significantly influencing their abundance. The main diet of many species includes honeydew from aphids (Domisch et al., 2009). The species of the *Formica rufa* group harvest their food mainly from tree canopies and can effectively reduce herbivore pressure (Wellenstein, 1952). According to extensive studies, almost half of their food consists of insects, including species considered “forest pests” thus keeping the ecological balance in the forests (Hölldobler & Wilson, 1990; Robinson & Stockan, 2020; Van Buggenum, 2022). The ants may also have a positive effect on soil properties because their nest material contains concentrated minerals bound to organic materials (Risch et al. 2005). Trees near the nests can use the nutrients, resulting in accelerated growth (Fürjes-

Mikó et al., 2019), a feature extremely important for the protected areas.

Red wood ants in Bulgaria and Rila Mountain

Red wood ants in Bulgaria include *Formica lugubris* Zetterstedt, 1838, *F. polyctena* Förster, 1850, *F. pratensis* Retzius, 1783, *F. rufa* Linnaeus, 1761, *F. aquilonia* Yarrow, 1955 and *F. truncorum* Fabricius, 1804 (Lapeva-Gjonova & Antonova, 2022). The first summarised records on RWA in Bulgaria were published by Otto et al. (1962). A National Inventory of RWA in Bulgaria was conducted in 1970–1973 and the results are reported in Bobev (1972, 1973) and Vatov & Bobev (1976). Current data regarding the distribution and density of RWA in Bulgaria at the national level for 2014 was published by Antonova & Marinov (2021).

The following species of red wood ants have been reported for Rila Mt: *Formica aquilonia* Zavrachitsa hut (Wesselinoff, 1973); *Formica lugubris* (Rila Mt: Bobev, 1972; Wesselinoff, 1973, 1979; Atanassov, 1974; Vatov & Bobev, 1976; Vesselinov, 1981); under Ibar Peak, Borovets (Otto et al., 1962; Atanassov & Dlusskij, 1992), Parangalitsa Reserve (Wesselinoff, 1968, 1973), Semkovo (Wesselinoff, 1973), Rila Monastery (Gateva, 1975), Ibar Reserve (Atanassov, 1983); *Formica polyctena* Malyovitsa Peak, southwest of Govedartsi Village (Atanassov & Dlusskij, 1992); *Formica pratensis* (Rila Mt: Forel, 1892; Otto et al., 1962; Bobev, 1972; Wesselinoff, 1973); Ibar Reserve (Atanassov, 1983); *Formica rufa* (Rila Mt: Wesselinoff, 1973, 1979; Atanassov, 1974; Vesselinov, 1981; Atanassov & Dlusskij, 1992); Rilska River Valley (Forel, 1892), Borovets (Atanassov, 1934), Parangalitsa Reserve (Wesselinoff, 1968), Govedartsi Village, Borovets, Raduil, Kostenets (Otto et al., 1962), Ibar Reserve (Atanassov, 1983), Panichishte (Lapeva-Gjonova, 2004). *Formica exsecta* Nylander, 1846 is a red wood ant species, although it is not a member of the *rufa* group (true red wood ants). It has a similar ecological role in ecosystems as true RWA. It has been reported for Rila Mt by Wesselinoff (1973, 1979), Vesselinov (1981), Atanassov & Dlusskij (1992), Elenin Peak (Forel, 1892), the Parangalitsa Reserve (Wesselinoff, 1968, 1973) and Ibar Reserve (Atanassov, 1983).

Most studies related to the species diversity of RWA in Rila Mt were published more than 50 years ago, and nearly all of them are faunistic studies that

do not concern nest density. Preliminary data on the myrmecofauna of Parangalitsa Biosphere Reserve were reported by Antonova & Kyonev (2023).

Conservation

RWA are considered species of special conservation measures in Europe (IUCN, 2023). They are recognised as Lower Risk/Near Threatened species and are included in the CORINE biotopes (2000) checklist (Annex 4). In Bulgaria, RWA have been under protection since 1959 (Izvestiya, 1959). Additionally, *Formica rufa* is protected by the Bulgarian Biological Diversity Act (2002) in Annex 2 and 3.

Due to recent monitoring efforts, it is possible to establish the current state of the populations of the RWA species, as well as make predictions regarding the trends in their nest density. The present monitoring investigation aims to: 1) assess the current RWA species diversity, 2) assess the spatial distribution of RWA, and 3) gather preliminary data on the trends of RWA nest density in Rila Mt over 8 years for conservation purposes.

Material and methods

Study area

This study is part of two national monitoring projects of the Bulgarian Ministry of Environment and Water conducted in May–September 2014, and 2022, in the mountainous regions of Bulgaria. Rila Mt was one of the investigated areas. It is the highest mountain in the Balkan Peninsula in southwestern Bulgaria (Musala Peak 2925 m a.s.l.). The climate is humid continental and Alpine climate at the highest parts (Georgiev, 1986). The forests of coniferous zone between 1600 m and 2100 m consist primarily of Norway spruce (*Picea abies* (Linnaeus, 1753) Karsten), Balkan pine (*Pinus peuce* Grisebach, 1844) and Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris* Linnaeus, 1753); the sub-Alpine zone up to 2500 m is covered by dwarf mountain pine (*Pinus mugo* Turra, 1764) and common juniper (*Juniperus communis* Linnaeus, 1753) (Georgiev, 1986). The studied localities included the northern border of the Parangalitsa Biosphere Reserve, the Rila Monastery region (Rilska Reka Valley), and the Samokov area, in the northern part of the mountain (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. The nests of red wood ants (circles) in the studied region.

Sampling method

The transect sampling method was used in the potential habitats of the red wood ants. Each transect was 250 m long and 5 m wide (i.e. 1250 m² per transect) and was situated in a homogeneous biotope (Borkin et al., 2012). Twenty-nine sampling transects were investigated in 2014 (3.625 ha) and 27 (19 with nests + 8 additional) transects in 2022 (3.375 ha) in Rila Mt. Empty transects (without nests) were not rechecked in 2022. The additional sampling transects in 2022 were included for greater representativeness of the data for further statistical analyses at the national level. All visible nests (active and abandoned) were counted, marked with GPS coordinates, photographed, and their diameter and height were measured. The results include only transects with active or abandoned nests.

The identification of the specimens was done using a stereomicroscope Olympus SZX 9 and preserved in the collection of V. Antonova at IBER-BAS.

Target species

The target species were the red wood ants included in the National System for Environmental Monitoring

list of Executive Environment Agency (MOEW): *Formica rufa*, *F. pratensis*, *F. lugubris* and *F. polyctena*. In 2014, *Formica exsecta* was added to the list.

Results

In 2014, 35 nests of red wood ants were found in Rila Mt, and 83 nests (76 active and 7 abandoned) were found in 2022. The nests of *F. rufa* included 39 active and 4 abandoned mounds. *Formica lugubris* was represented with 14 active nests, *F. pratensis* – with 12 active and 3 abandoned nests, and *F. exsecta* – with 11 active nests. The distribution of nests by region and species is presented below.

1. Parangalitsa Biosphere Reserve

In total, 8 nests of *Formica rufa*, *F. lugubris* and *F. exsecta* were found, marked, and measured in 2014, and 27 nests (25 active, of which 19 newly found) were found in 2022 (Fig. 1, Table. 1).

The most abundant species was *F. exsecta* (9,78 nests/ha in 2022). The real nest number was much higher because *F. exsecta* typically establishes numer-

Table 1. Number, density (nests/ha) and condition of red wood ant nests in the Parangalitsa Biosphere Reserve by year.

Species	2014		2022								
	Active nests / 5 tracks (0.625 ha)		Abandoned old nests / 5 tracks (0.625 ha)		Active old nests / 5 tracks (0.625 ha)			Active newly found nests / 4 tracks (0.5 ha)		Active nests total / 9 tracks (1.125 ha)	
	N	density	N	%	N	density	%	N	density	N	density
<i>F. rufa</i>	3	4.8	2	67	1	1.6	33	5	10	6	5.3
<i>F. lugubris</i>	2	3.2	0	0	2	3.2	100	6	12	8	7.1
<i>F. exsecta</i>	3	4.8	0	0	3	4.8	100	8	16	11	9.8
Total	8	12.8	2	25	6	9.6	75	19	38	25	22.2

Fig. 2. *Formica rufa* nest in Parangalitsa Biosphere Reserve with unchanged size and condition: A [left] – 2014; B [right] – 2022.

ous daughter colonies which in our case were not counted due to the limited size of the transects. In 2022, *F. lugubris* was represented in the area of the transects by nest density of 7.1 active nests/ha, and *F. rufa* was represented by 5.3 active nests/ha.

In the area sampled in 2014, 6 of the 8 active nests were re-found. Of the old active nests re-marked in 2022, three (one nest of each species) appeared unchanged in size (Fig. 2A, B). Two (67%) of the

three nests of *F. rufa* have been abandoned (Fig. 3). The nest density of *F. rufa* decreased from 4.8 to 1.6 nests/ha in the revisited 5 transects (Table 1).

2. Rila Monastery region

In total, 5 nests of *F. rufa* and *F. pratensis* were found, marked and measured in 2014, whereas the total num-

Fig. 3. *Formica rufa* nest condition in Parangalitsa Biosphere Reserve after an 8-years period: A [left] – alive (2014); B [right] – abandoned (2022).

Table 2. Number, density (nests/ha) and condition of red wood ant nests in the Rila Monastery region by years.

Species	2014		2022								
	Active nests / 8 tracks (1 ha)		Abandoned old nests / 4 tracks (0.5 ha)		Active old nests / 4 tracks (0.5 ha)			Active newly found nests / 4 old tracks + 1 new track (0.625 ha)		Active nests total / 5 tracks (0.625 ha)	
	N	density	N	%	N	density	%	N	density	N	density
<i>F. rufa</i>	2	2	1	50	1	2	50	4	6.4	5	8
<i>F. pratensis</i>	3	2	0	0	3	6	100	4	6.4	7	11.2
Total	5	5	1	20	4	8	80	8	12.8	12	19.2

Fig. 4. *Formica rufa* nest condition in Kirilova Polyana region after an 8-year period: A [left] – alive in 2014; B [right] – abandoned in 2022.

Table 3. Number, density (nests/ha) and condition of red wood ant nests in Samokov region by years.

Species	2014		2022								
	Active nests/ 13 tracks (1.625 ha)		Abandoned old nests / 9 tracks (1.125 ha)		Active old nests / 9 tracks (1.125 ha)			Active newly found nests / 9 old+2 new tracks (1.375 ha)		Active nests total / 11 tracks (1.375 ha)	
	N	density	N	%	N	density	%	N	density	N	density
<i>F. rufa</i>	10	6.1	1	10	7	6.2	70	35	25.5	28	20.4
<i>F. lugubris</i>	7	4.3	0	0	6	5.3	86	0	0	6	4.4
<i>F. pratensis</i>	5	3.1	3	60	2	1.8	40	3	2.2	5	3.6
Total	22	13.5	4	18	15	13.3	68	24	17.4	39	28.4

Fig. 5. *Formica pratensis* nest condition in Samokov region after 8 years: A [left] – alive in 2014; B [right] – abandoned in 2022.

ber of nests in 2022 was 12 (4 active old nests and 8 newly found nests) (Table 2). The sole abandoned nest of *F. rufa* is presented in Fig. 4.

3. Samokov region

In total, 22 nests of *F. rufa*, *F. lugubris*, and *F. pratensis* were found, marked, and measured in 2014, whereas the total number of nests in 2022 was 39 (15 active old nests and 24 newly found nests from additional transects) (Fig. 1, Table 3). Two nests of *F.*

polycтена × rufa hybrid were found in 2014 near Govedartsi Village (Antonova & Marinov, 2021) but not re-found in 2022.

The number of old nests found in 2022 does not match those from 2014 because not all of the mounds were found. For example, in the Samokov region 2 nests of *F. rufa* were not found (20%) and one nest of *F. lugubris* was not found (14%). One out of 10 nests (10%) of *F. rufa* have been abandoned. In 2022, 35 new nests of *F. rufa* were found along 9 old and 2 new transects at forest ecotones/sunny meadows with single trees. Three of

the five nests (60%) of *F. pratensis* have been abandoned (Fig. 5). The nest density of *F. pratensis* has decreased from 3.1 to 1.8 nests/ha in the revisited 9 transects (Table 3).

Discussion

We confirmed four of the six RWA species reported from Rila Mt: *F. lugubris*, *F. rufa* and *F. pratensis*, as well as *F. exsecta* (red wood ant, not *rufa* group). The two nests similar to *F. polyctena*, found in the course of this study, were identified as *F. polyctena* × *rufa* hybrid. *Formica aquilonia* was not found in the studied mountains during the latest monitoring programs (2014–2022). The spatial distribution of RWA in Rila Mt is in accordance with the elevational preferences of these taxa (Atanassov & Dlusskij, 1992; Antonova & Marinov, 2021): the lowest parts (600–1300 m) of the sampling area were occupied by *F. pratensis*, the mid-elevational areas (1050 up to 1560 m) by *F. rufa* (most abundant at 1200–1300 m), whereas *F. lugubris* and *F. exsecta* were naturally found in the highest parts (1500–2000 m).

The abandoned (dead) nests were still recognisable, probably due to the slower degradation rate of the pine needles in the nest material as suggested by Juhász et al. (2020). Contrary to Juhász et al. (2020), the abandoned nests in our study were not situated close to larger nests. If nest relocation was the reason for nest abandonment, the distances in our cases should be greater than those observed by Juhász and colleagues (more than 30 m, which was the radius of visible area around each of our transects). According to Burns et al. (2020), in *F. lugubris* the rate of nest abandonment decreases after 2 years and is lower in larger nests. In our study we did not register any abandoned nests of *F. lugubris* for 8 years (2014–2022). We found abandoned nests of *F. rufa* in the revisited transects in the three regions with a total abandonment ratio of 9.3%. Abandoned nests of *F. pratensis* were found only in the northern part of Rila Mt (Samokov region), with an abandonment ratio of 20%.

All three species of red wood ants reported by Wesselinov (1968), and Wesselinoff (1973) for the Parangalitsa Biosphere Reserve's region were confirmed 50 years later. Despite that our monitoring sampling area was in the vicinity of the reserve, the most widespread species still was *F. exsecta*, with

huge colonies containing dozens of nests in the alpine meadows. The same habitat was reported for the reserve's interior by Wesselinov (1968). According to the author, the most abundant RWA was *F. exsecta* in the hills' meadows between the rivers Haydushka, Golyama Parangalitsa and Malka Parangalitsa, which were at a similar elevation as the areas in our study. *Formica lugubris* occupied the same open habitats but was also found in areas of *Juniperus* sp. shrubs and the ecotone of sparse *Picea abies* forest with smaller number of nests in a colony. Still, *F. rufa* was the species with the smallest number of nests in the region. Wesselinov (1968) noted only 2 nests of this species in the interior of the reserve. At this elevation, *F. rufa* is expected to be less represented than the other RWA species because it reaches the upper limit of its distribution (about 1600 m a.s.l.) at the northwestern edge of the reserve (Atanassov & Dlusskij, 1992). According to Antonova & Marinov (2021), elevation and canopy cover are the habitat characteristics of primary importance for the distribution and nest density of *F. lugubris* and *F. rufa* in Bulgaria. The authors found that the optimal nest density of *F. rufa* was between 40% and 80% canopy cover. As the Biosphere Reserve Parangalitsa has been designated as a reserve since 1933 (Darzhaven vestnik, 1933), wood clearance, removal of old fallen wood, and felling have been strongly forbidden in the hundred-years-old forests. As a consequence, the forest interior is much closed (over 80% canopy cover). The abandoned nests situation is much similar in the Rila Monastery and Samokov regions, both of which contain dense old forests. As a species nesting in sun-warmed places (Babik et al., 2009), *F. rufa* is extremely sensitive to shading of its habitat. In our study, the nests of *F. rufa* were found only in the vicinity of the forest, around roads, and in open sunny spots. Our observations of abandoned nests in the revisited transects 8 years later corroborated the conclusions of Collingwood (1979), Punttila et al. (1994), Dekoninck et al. (2010), Tsikas et al. (2016), and Serttaş et al. (2020) that RWA (and especially *F. rufa*) nest density declines with increased canopy closure. New nests appeared in sunlit habitats, which was also observed in other Bulgarian mountains during the last national monitoring study in 2022 (Antonova, unpubl. data). Small interventions, such as forest thinning or clearing to create open sunny spots in the vicinity of the reserve would support the existence of *F. rufa*. These measures include creating

small clearings in dense forests and reducing shading due to overgrowing shrubs or herbaceous plants (Van Buggenum, 2022). The protection and enhancement of their habitats are needed for the sustainability of the ecosystems (Stockan & Robinson, 2016; Yilmaz et al., 2023).

None of the abandoned nests of *F. pratensis* were relocated near the track area. Because of the overgrown shrubs *Rosa canina* Linnaeus, 1753 and *Rubus* sp. near the nests, we assume that the most probable explanation for the ants' "evacuation" is again the shading of their habitat. Under such conditions, the ants' microhabitat becomes humid and excessively dark (especially at the ecotones). In the location near Samokov City, the grasses have grown taller, and shrubs have appeared in 2022 as compared to 2014. Although in Central Europe *F. pratensis* has been reported in both dark and light areas independent of undergrowth density (Véle et al. 2009), Mabelis & Korczyńska (2016) suggested that this species prefers dry localities in open stands, avoids dense undergrowth and bushes shading and cooling of its habitat, and that dense grass cover obstructs the ants during foraging. Another reason for the ants' disappearance could be the physical damage to the nests by large herbivores and humans (Kiss & Kobori, 2010), as the nests of *F. pratensis* are usually situated in meadows at the edge of the forest. Climate warming and prolonged drought may also harm RWA as boreal species, but this impact has not yet been studied (Sorvari, 2022).

Many factors including food supply, microclimate, competition with other ant species, type of social organisation of the colony and dispersal ability affect the habitat requirements of wood ants (Camplitepe & Askoy, 2019). For a viable colony, these territorial species require at least a few hectares of stable habitat with enough food resources to maintain sexual forms for reproduction (Dekoninck et al., 2010). Generally, the Rila National Park, including Parangalitsa Biosphere Reserve, provides such conditions to a great extent and abandoned nests are only about 8% across all four RWA species. The loss, shading, drying/flooding, disturbance or destruction of habitat are the major threats to RWA. The changes in the nest density we ascertained for 8 years support the claim that at least 5 years of monitoring are needed to compare changes across regions (e.g. Zakharov et al., 2013), detect trends in RWA populations, and evaluate the effects of protection measures.

Conclusions

1. Four of the six species of red wood ants reported from Rila Mt were confirmed: *F. lugubris*, *F. rufa* and *F. pratensis*, as well as the non *rufa* group *F. exsecta*. *Formica polyctena* × *rufa* hybrid was identified in the two nests with specimens similar to *F. polyctena*, found in 2014. *Formica aquilonia* was not confirmed in Rila Mt during the latest monitoring programs (2014–2022).
2. The species diversity of the red wood ants in the region of Parangalitsa Biosphere Reserve has not changed in the last 50 years. Despite the sampling area being situated at the northern border of the reserve, the approximate occurrence of the three RWA species (*F. exsecta*, *F. lugubris* and *F. rufa*) was confirmed, and the first species was represented with the highest nest density.
3. The spatial distribution of RWA in Rila Mt is in accordance with the elevational preferences of the species: the lowest parts of the sampling area were occupied by *F. pratensis*, the mid-elevational areas – by *F. rufa*, while *F. lugubris* and *F. exsecta* were naturally found in the higher parts of the mountain.
4. A decline in the nest density of *F. rufa* and *F. pratensis* in some areas of Rila Mt is observed after an 8-year period (2014–2022). The percentage of abandoned nests can be explained by the increased shading of the habitats in the old forests of the Rila National Park. Monitoring is recommended at least every 5 years.

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Authors' contribution

(using [CrediT](#))

Vera Antonova: conceptualisation, data curation, formal analysis, investigation, methodology, validation,

visualisation, writing—original draft, writing—review and editing; Dimitar Kyonev: data curation, investigation, writing—review and editing; Martin Marinov: formal analysis, validation, writing—review and editing.

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